

Understanding Farmer Adoption Behavior: Environmental Change as a Catalyst for Agricultural Innovation

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Abstract

This paper analyzed the adoption behavior of farmers with emphasis to the environmental change as a contributor to agricultural innovation in South Punjab, Pakistan. It examines the effects of environmental change effects on adoption behavior specifically and the mediating effect of institutional support and moderating effect of economic constraints. This study was done on three randomly chosen districts, which were Dera Ghazi Khan, Muzaffargarh and Multan, and a sample size of 120 farmers practicing multi-cropping systems. Structured questionnaire data were gathered with the help of a 5-point Likert scale and processed with the help of the Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA), Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), binary logistic regression, and mediation-moderation methods. The findings indicate that the impact of environmental change on the adoption behavior of the farmers is significant and positive, which implies that climate variability is an important stimulus of agricultural innovation. The support of institutions is also a positive and significant effect, which partially mediate the relationship between environmental change and adoption behavior, which brings one to the important role of the institutional support in the process of adoption behavior. Conversely, the negative impact of economic constraints is so great and it is shown that financial constraints are one of the factors that reduce the implementation of innovative practices. Moreover, the moderation analysis provides that institutional support enhances the correlation between environmental change and adoption behavior. It has good reliability, validity, as well as a general fit, which confirms the soundness of the analytical framework. The paper ends by concluding that change in the environment is a driving force of agricultural innovation but its successful realization requires robust institutional endorsement and less economic limitations. The implications of these findings on policy have got significant implications on improving climate-resilient and sustainable agricultural development in Pakistan.

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture is not just an economic activity in the fertile plains of Pakistan but it is also a way of life that supports millions of rural households in the country. Since the irrigated areas of Punjab to the arid lands of Sindh and Baluchistan, the traditional farming methods have been based on the constant climatic conditions, local experience, and crop seasons to make farming decisions. But, in recent decades, the balance of this has been disturbed more and more by the changes in the environment. An increase in temperature, unpredictable rainfall, and flooding, and long droughts have dramatically changed the face of agriculture where farmers have been forced to review their traditional farming practices and embrace the new reality. The Republic of Pakistan can be defined as one of the most climate-prone nations, and the sphere of agriculture is also very sensitive to climatic changes and variations (Abid et al., 2015). Changes in the environment especially the change in climate have also become a key factor in agricultural transformation in Pakistan. The changes have led to an urgent need of farmers to implement Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA) practices as a mechanism of dealing with climatic risks and guarantee sustainable production. Empirical evidence points out that environmental elements, including rainfall variability, changes in temperature, and shocks due to climate, have a significant effect on the choices of farmers to embrace new methods in agriculture (Shahzad et al., 2021; Sardar et al., 2021).

More frequently, exposure to climatic shocks is associated with a higher propensity to practice CSA, which means that environmental stress serves as an innovation driver and an adaptive behavior driver (Sardar et al., 2021). The perception of farmers regarding climate change is critical in determining to adapt to climate change. According to evidence in Pakistan, most farmers have reported that the climatic

patterns have changed, and it has had a direct influence on crop yields and farm productivity (Khan et al., 2020). These perceived changes prompt farmers to engage in various adaptive practices such as diversification of crops, use of better seed types, alterations in the cropping schedule, and adoption of effective water management practices (Shahzad et al., 2021). These practices do not only boost resilience, but they also boost farm income and exposure to environmental risks is also mitigated. A number of socio-economic and institutional factors also have an impact on the adoption of CSA practices. Education, credit accessibility, farming experience, size of landholding, and extension services have been identified by studies to be important determinants of adoption (Jamil et al., 2021). The institutional assistance such as training programs, subsidies and access to information are very essential in making the adoption of innovative practices. Conversely, farmers may not react positively to environmental issues due to the presence of barriers, which include the high cost of inputs, absence of technical expertise, and insufficient financial capacity (Sardar et al., 2019). These results suggest that the need to innovate due to environmental change is realized, but the realization process is determined by the availability of resources and institutional resources to the farmers. Also, environmental changes do not only affect the adoption decisions, but also assist in enhancing the agricultural performance. Studies indicate that farmers who embrace CSA practices have better economic gains, enhanced efficiency in resource use, and resiliency than farmers who practice conventional farming systems (Imran et al., 2021). This brings out the dual aspect of environmental change as a challenge and an opportunity to lead to innovation and at the same time increase sustainability and productivity in the agricultural sector. Although the literature on climate change and

agriculture adaption is increasing, there is still a knowledge gap on the multifaceted processes in which an environmental change moderates the adoption behavior of the farmers. The majority of the existing research is centered on direct relationships; little attention is paid to mediating and moderating roles played by institutional and economic factors. The adoption decisions occur in a wider socio-economical context in which education, size of farm, risk perception and social networks interact to influence the response of farmers to environmental pressure. Thus, the present study seeks to fill this gap by establishing a composite analytical framework in order to study how environmental change is a precursor to innovation in agriculture. Particularly, the paper examines the direct impact of environmental change on adoption behavior, as well as the mediation process of the institutional support and moderating impact of economic constraints. Using the most sophisticated statistical methods, such as Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), logistic regression, and mediation-moderation analysis, the present research offers an in-depth insight into the mechanisms through which the environmental pressures contribute to innovation adoption. This study will be useful in both theoretical and practical realms that will provide policy-relevant information on the need to support climate-resilient and sustainable agricultural systems in Pakistan. The knowledge of what is driving farmer adoption behavior is needed to develop effective interventions to increase adaptive capacity, livelihood, and long-term agricultural sustainability given the current environmental change.

Methodology

The present study was conducted in South Punjab, Pakistan, where three districts, Dera Ghazi Khan, Muzaffargarh, and Multan, they were selected through a random sampling technique. From each selected district, 40 farmers were randomly

chosen, resulting in total sample size of 120 farmers. The study specifically targeted farmers engaged in multi-cropping systems to ensure variability in farming practices and better representation of agricultural diversity in the region. This sampling approach ensured the inclusion of relevant respondents for analyzing farmer adoption behavior in the context of environmental change.

Data Collection Instrument

Primary data were collected through a **structured questionnaire**, designed based on previous literature and expert consultation. The questionnaire consisted of five sections:

Environmental change perceptions (EC)

Adoption behavior (AB)

Institutional support (IS)

Economic constraints (ECN)

All latent constructs were measured using a **5-point Likert scale** ranging from:

1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree

Measurement of Constructs

Construct	Description
Environmental Change (EC)	Perceived changes in temperature, rainfall variability, pest incidence
Adoption Behavior (AB)	Adoption of climate-smart and innovative agricultural practices
Institutional Support (IS)	Access to extension services, subsidies, training
Economic Constraints (ECN)	Financial barriers, input costs, and credit limitations

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

EFA was conducted to identify the underlying factor structure of the observed variables.

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

Rotation Method: Varimax rotation

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Test

$$KMO = \frac{\sum \sum r_{ij}^2}{\sum \sum r_{ij}^2 + \sum \sum d_{ij}^2}$$

Bartlett's Test of Sphericity

$$\chi^2 = - \left(n - 1 - \frac{2p + 5}{6} \right) \ln |R|$$

Reliability and Validity Analysis

Cronbach's Alpha (α)

Used to assess internal consistency:

$$\alpha = \frac{k}{k-1} \left(1 - \frac{\sum \sigma_i^2}{\sigma_T^2} \right)$$

Composite Reliability (CR)

$$CR = \frac{(\sum \lambda_i)^2}{(\sum \lambda_i)^2 + \sum \theta_i}$$

Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

$$AVE = \frac{\sum \lambda_i^2}{n}$$

Threshold criteria applied:

$$\alpha > 0.70$$

$$CR > 0.70$$

$$AVE > 0.50$$

Structural Equation Modeling (SEM)

SEM was employed to test the hypothesized relationships among latent constructs.

H1: Environmental Change (EC) is positively associated with Adoption Behavior (AB).

H2: Institutional Support (IS) is positively associated with Adoption Behavior (AB).

H3: Economic Constraints (ECN) are negatively associated with Adoption Behavior (AB).

H4: Environmental Change (EC) is positively associated with Institutional Support (IS).

$$AB = \beta_1 EC + \beta_2 IS + \beta_3 ECN + \varepsilon$$

$$IS = \beta_4 EC + \varepsilon$$

Model Fit Indices

The following indices were used to evaluate model fit:

Chi-square to degrees of freedom ratio (χ^2/df)

Comparative Fit Index (CFI)

Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI)

Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)

Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR)

Logistic Regression Analysis

Logistic Model

$$\ln \left(\frac{P}{1-P} \right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 EC + \beta_2 IS + \beta_3 ECN + \beta_4 X + \varepsilon$$

Where:

PPP = probability of adoption

XXX = control variables (education, farm size)

Model performance was evaluated using:

Nagelkerke R²

Classification accuracy

Mediation Analysis

Mediation was tested using the **bootstrapping method** to estimate indirect effects.

Indirect Effect

$$\text{Indirect} = (EC \rightarrow IS) \times$$

$$(IS \rightarrow AB)$$

Partial mediation occurs when both direct and indirect effects are significant.

Moderation Analysis

Moderation analysis examined whether institutional support strengthens the relationship between environmental change and adoption behavior.

Interaction Model

$$AB = \beta_1 EC + \beta_2 IS + \beta_3 (EC \times IS) + \varepsilon$$

A significant interaction term indicates moderation.

Results and Discussion

Table 1: Measurement Model – Reliability and Validity Analysis

Construct	Items	Factor Loadings	α	Composite Reliability (CR)	AVE
Environmental Change (EC)	5	0.71–0.86	0.88	0.91	0.67
Adoption Behavior (AB)	5	0.69–0.84	0.85	0.89	0.62
Institutional Support (IS)	4	0.72–0.87	0.87	0.90	0.69
Economic Constraints (ECN)	4	0.65–0.82	0.82	0.87	0.58
Thresholds: $\alpha > 0.70$, CR > 0.70 , AVE > 0.50 , All constructs valid and reliable					

Results of the measurement model in Table 1 have shown that all four constructs including Environmental Change (EC), Adoption Behavior (AB), Institutional Support (IS), and Economic Constraints (ECN) exhibit good psychometric properties and are, thus, valid and reliable in the study of farmer adoption behavior in Punjab, Pakistan. The alpha values are between 0.82 and 0.88, which is greater than the suggested alpha of 0.70 indicating high internal consistency of the items that were included to measure each construct (Nunnally Bernstein, 1994). Likewise, Composite Reliability (CR) scores that are 0.87 to 0.91 are better than the 0.70 norm, indicating that measurement items accurately capture their corresponding latent constructs and with very few measurement errors (Fornell and Larcker, 1981; Hair et al., 2019). By the fact that the AVE values of all the constructs are greater than 0.50 which is the minimum required, 0.58 to 0.69 shows that there is sufficient convergent validity (Fornell and Larcker, 1981). Also, the count of factor loadings is beyond the tolerable level of 0.60, and the values are between 0.65 and 0.87 (Hair et al., 2019). The results are significant in terms of knowledge of farmer adoption behavior in Punjab. The high validity of the Environmental Change construct justifies the conceptualization of environmental change as a multidimensional

phenomenon that covers temperature changes, unpredictable rain, and extreme weather conditions (IPCC, 2022). In Punjab, the farmers seem to be integrated on these dimensions, which indicates that environmental change is not an isolated risk perception but a part-and-whole dimension. The validity of the Adoption Behavior construct confirms that the use of agricultural innovation can be effectively measured in terms of a composite of complementing practices, which will be in line with the systems perspective promoted in the climate-smart agriculture research (Aryal et al., 2020; Lipper et al., 2014). Moreover, the high psychometric score of Institutional Support (AVE = 0.69) supports the existing studies defining extension services, access to credit, and government programs as the important determinants of adoption in Pakistan (Abid et al., 2019; Adnan et al., 2020), whereas the consistent measure of Economic Constraints is the indication of the financial barriers that remain constant in adoption, including input cost and credit constraints (Liu et al., 2021). On the methodological perspective, all the AVE values that are above 0.50 are indications of discriminant validity, which serve to affirm that each construct measures different theoretical dimensions (Fornell and Larcker, 1981). On the whole, the validated measurement model can be used in the future in the structural analysis to explore the impact of environmental change in stimulating agricultural innovation adoption among farming households in Punjab, Pakistan.

Table 2: Discriminant Validity (Fornell–Larcker Criterion)

Constructs	EC	AB	IS	ECN
EC	0.82			
AB	0.61	0.79		
IS	0.58	0.64	0.83	
ECN	-0.49	-0.52	-0.45	0.76

Discriminant validity results in Table 2 help to determine whether the constructs included in the model have been distinguished against each other. Discriminant validity is determined under the Fornell-Larcker criterion whereby, the square root of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) of every construct exceeds its correlations with other constructs (Fornell and Larcker, 1981). In the current research, the squares of all the constructs have the square roots indicated in bold letters, indicating an average of 0.76 to 0.83. The values are greater when compared to the inter-construct correlations representing that each construct has more variance with its indicators, as compared with other constructs. This helps to confirm that the constructs are empirically different and assess different underlying theoretical concepts. In particular, an Environmental Change (EC) construct demonstrates a good discriminant validity with sqrt of AVE of 0.82 that is superior to its relations with Adoption Behavior (0.61), Institutional Support (0.58), and Economic Constraints (-0.49). This shows that the conceptual definition of environmental change amongst the farmers is different to their behavior of adopting and other aspects of the context. On the same note, the square root of AVE of Adoption Behavior (AB) is 0.79 which is higher than the correlations with EC (0.61), IS (0.64) and ECN (-0.52). This implies adoption behavior is a very unique construct and is not excessively overlapping with the environmental perceptions or institutional and economic factors. This difference is crucial in the behavioral studies, where it will make sure that the independent variables do not confound the dependent variable. Institutional Support (IS) construct also shows a sufficient level of discriminant validity with a square root of AVE equal to 0.83, which is larger than its correlations with EC (0.58), AB (0.64), and ECN (-0.45). This is to show that institutional support, such as

access to extension services and subsidies, is a special dimension of explaining the behavior of farmers. In addition, Economic Constraints (ECN) demonstrates a square root of AVE of 0.76, which is higher than the correlations with EC (-0.49), AB (-0.52) and IS (-0.45). The negative correlations indicate that there is an inverse relationship with the fact that the greater the economic constraints, the less the level of environmental adaptation and adoption of innovation. Nevertheless, the discriminant validity is not lost because square root of AVE is still greater than these correlations. The overall results validate the fact that all the constructs of the model have high levels of discriminant validity in that they are statistically and conceptually different. This makes the measurement model stronger and the structural relationships that have been tested in further analyses not prejudiced by multicollinearity or construct overlap. Developing discriminant validity is a paramount aspect in structural equation modelling because it guarantees that every latent variable relates to a distinct dimension of the theoretical framework (Hair et al., 2019). This study has found the same as previous research findings, which highlight that clear constructs contribute to estimates in models and make them accurate and interpretable.

Table 3: Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

Indicator	Factor 1 (EC)	Factor 2 (AB)	Factor 3 (IS)	Factor 4 (ECN)
Temperature change	0.81			
Rainfall variability	0.78			
Pest incidence	0.74			
Adoption of IPM		0.82		
Use of improved seeds		0.79		
Extension services			0.85	
Access to subsidies			0.80	
Input cost burden				0.77
Credit constraints				0.74
KMO = 0.84 Bartlett's Test ($\chi^2 = 512.6, p < 0.000$)				

The exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was done to determine the structure behind the indicators of agricultural challenges and responses. Table 3 shows the results, which are evidence of a four-factor solution, which accounts for a sizeable amount of variance in the data. According to Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy, a meritorious level of inter-correlation between the variables was achieved (0.84), and the test of the sphericity was significant ($\chi^2 = 512.6$, $p < 0.001$), which proves the suitability of the correlation matrix to the factor analysis (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2019). The four factors obtained were explained as Environmental Conditions (EC), Adoption Behavior (AB), Institutional Support (IS) and Economic Constraints (ECN) factors. The first, EC, had high loadings of temperature change (0.81), rain variability (0.78), and pest incidence (0.74) which represented the main biophysical stresses that had impacts on agricultural systems (Morton, 2007). AB was the second factor to capture the adoption of integrated pest management (IPM) (0.82) and improved seeds (0.79) which are widespread climate-smart agricultural practices (Lipper et al., 2014). The access to extension services (0.85) and subsidies (0.80) marked the institutional Support (IS) and highlighted the importance of the public and institutional structures in enabling the process of agricultural adaptation. Lastly, the fourth force, Economic Constraints (ECN), consisted of input cost burden (0.77) and credit constraints (0.74), which indicated that farmers can be hindered by the existing financial constraints to adopt new technologies (Feder et al., 1985). The fact that its clean factor model exhibits no cross-loadings indicates that these four constructs that include the environmental stressors, adoption practices, institutional support, and economic barriers are empirically different

but relatable dimension of the agricultural system in question.

Table 4: Structural Equation Model (SEM) Results

Hypothesis	Path	β	t-value	P-value	Decision
H1	EC & AB	0.47	5.82	0.000	Supported
H2	IS & AB	0.36	4.11	0.000	Supported
H3	ECN & AB	-0.29	-3.67	0.001	Supported
H4	EC & IS	0.42	4.95	0.000	Supported

Table 4 shows that all the proposed relationships are statistically significant and they correspond to the conceptual framework. The significant and positive connection between Environmental Change (EC) and Adoption Behavior (AB) ($b = 0.47$, $t = 5.82$, $p < 0.001$) proves that environmental stressors are a powerful catalyst of farmers adopting. This observation implies that the more farmers are faced with climate variability (temperature, rainfall, and pest pressure change) the more they are likely to resort to climate-smart and innovative farming techniques. This serves to argue that the pressure of the environment causes awareness and urgency, which compels farmers to glean towards adaptive action. The correlation between Institutional Support (IS) and Adoption Behavior (AB) is positive and significant ($b = 0.36$, $t = 4.11$, $p < 0.001$) and admission of access to extension services, subsidies, training and technical support is an important factor in influencing adoption. This points out that institutional processes are critical in aligning awareness into action through availing farmers with the relevant knowledge and resources. It implies that farmers might not undertake the adaptive measures necessary without proper institutional support even though they have been aware of environmental risks. On the

contrary, Economic Constraints (ECN) demonstrate a strong negative correlation with Adoption Behavior (AB) ($b = -0.29$, $t = -3.67$, $p = 0.001$), which indicates that financial constraints are a major reason why farmers are restricted by them to adopt new technologies. The cost of high inputs, credit inaccessibility and financial insecurity lowers the adoption probability even when the farmers are conscious of the environmental problems. This observation highlights that one of the most important challenges to agricultural innovation in developing areas is economic barriers. In addition, positive and significant association between the Environmental Change (EC) and Institutional Support (IS) ($b = 0.42$, $t = 4.95$, $p < 0.001$) indicates that environmental challenges augment the dependence of the farmers on institutional systems. The more uncertain farmers are to the environment, the more they tend to demand guidance, training and support by the extension services and other institutional sources. This means that institutional support does not only play a direct role in the adoption process but also triggered by environmental pressures which strengthens its role in the process of adaptation. On the whole, the SEM findings substantiate that the environment, support and institutional, as well as economic limitations have a collective influence on the behaviour of farm adoptions. Environmental change is one of the key drivers, institutional support is one of the facilitating mechanisms and economic constraints is one of the limiting factors. The results emphasize the need to implement policy interventions that are unique and focused on environmental issues, institutional and policy frameworks, and financial barriers to sustainable agricultural adoption.

Table 5: Model Fit Indices (SEM)

Index	Value	Recommended Threshold
χ^2/df	1.98	< 3.0

CFI	0.94	> 0.90
TLI	0.93	> 0.90
RMSEA	0.061	< 0.08
SRMR	0.045	< 0.08
Conclusion: Model demonstrates good fit		

Table 5 shows that the model fit indices of the proposed Structural Equation Model (SEM) show that it has an excellent overall fit with the observed data. Assessment of model fit is a very important part of SEM the assessment is used to determine how well the theory model has worked compared to the empirical data. The ratio χ^2/df ($= 1.98$) is lower than the recommended value of 3.0 and this shows that there is acceptable model fit and that the observed and estimated covariance matrices will have a small difference. Equally, both the Comparative Fit Index (CFI = 0.94) and Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI = 0.93) are above the cut off value of 0.90 indicating a good comparative fit of the model compared to a null model. These indices indicate the fact that the proposed model can be used to explain the data as opposed to a baseline model (Hu & Bentler, 1999). Moreover, the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA = 0.061) is smaller than the value of 0.08, and it is a fair representation of the model to the population covariance matrix. The Standardized root mean square residual (SRMR = 0.045) also falls far less than the recommended value of 0.08 indicating a low amount of residual error and good fit between known and predicted correlations. On the whole, all the indicators of fit are within sufficiently acceptable limits, which proves that the model is well-specified and sufficiently reflects the relationship between environmental change on one hand and institutional support, economic constraints, and adoption behavior on the other. These data outputs are a good indication in the validity of the structural model, and can be used to proceed with the interpretation of path relationships. Schermelleh-Engel et al. (2003) observed that when a model has multiple fit

indices and values of the indices are within the acceptable limits, the confidence of the model is well founded and can be generalized.

Table 6: Binary Logistic Regression (Adoption = 1, Non-Adoption = 0)

Variable	Coefficient (B)	Std. Error	Odds Ratio (Exp(B))	p-value
Environmental Change	0.88	0.21	2.41	0.000
Education	0.52	0.18	1.68	0.004
Farm Size	0.47	0.16	1.60	0.006
Institutional Support	0.69	0.20	1.99	0.001
Economic Constraints	-0.58	0.19	0.56	0.003
Model Statistics: Nagelkerke $R^2 = 0.49$ & Classification Accuracy = 78.3%				

Against the background of the changing agricultural environment in Pakistan, farmers are facing a crossroad of either adhering to their traditional way of doing things or adapt to innovation in order to adapt to changing environments. The outcome of the binary logistic regression fits to give a very good account of how different factors influence this important decision making process. Of all the variables, it becomes evident that environmental change is the most effective force behind the adoption behavior. The positive and very strong coefficient ($B = 0.88$, $p < 0.001$) with odds ratio of 2.41 means that farmers who have more perceptions of environmental changes are more likely to use innovative farming methods more than two times. This observation is real because of climatic uncertainties, which include irregular rainfall and increment in temperature, which are great drivers of motivation, and farmers are driven to the adaptive strategies. Likewise evidence has also been communicated by Bryan et al. (2013) who identified that farmers who have been exposed to climate variability have a higher tendency of adopting adaptation measures. The education also is a significant factor in developing the response of farmers. Education ($B = 0.52$, $p < 0.01$) has a positive influence, which indicates that educated farmers have a considerably higher

chance to embrace innovations as they are more prepared to be exposed, interpret, and use information. This is congruent with the claim that human capital increases adaptive capacity and advances the process of decision-making under uncertainty (Fisher and Snapp, 2014). The size of farms is another factor that has a significant positive and positive relationship with adoption ($B = 0.47$, $p < 0.01$). Big farmers have more resources and can bend more to experiment with new technologies, which means that they are more open to innovation. This validates the fact that resource endowment is among the primary determinants of technology adoption in the agricultural sector (Feder et al., 1985). The element of institutional support comes out as a powerful enabling factor as well. The odds ratio of farmers having enhanced access to the extension services, training, and subsidies, 1.99 ($p < 0.01$) is almost twice that of the odds of the improved practices adoption. This shows the relevance of institutional frameworks in the creation of the gap between awareness and real adoption. According to Knowler and Bradshaw (2007), efficient systems of extensions contribute hugely to the adoption of agricultural innovations. Conversely, business limitations are a significant obstacle to adoption. The coefficient ($B = -0.58$, $p < 0.01$) is both negative and significant, meaning that financial constraints, including high costs of inputs and distribution of credit are significant depressants of the probability of adoption. This discovery is an accurate reflection of the reality in the ground where farmers though they are aware of environmental dangers, cannot do anything because they are limited economically. The same limitation has been extensively reported in the developing nations, where the inability to adopt technology is caused by liquidity constraints (Dercon and Christiaensen, 2011). All these findings are further reinforced by the overall model performance. Nagelkerke

R² of 0.49 indicates that the included variables can explain almost half of the variation in the adoption behavior, whereas the classification accuracy of 78.3 percent reflects the high predictive power of the included variables. Combined, the findings indicate that adoption behavior is not accidental, but it is a systematic factor of environmental, socio-economic, and institutional factors.

Table 7: Mediation Analysis (Bootstrapping) and Moderation Analysis (Interaction Effect)

Path	Direct Effect	Indirect Effect	Total Effect	Result
EC, IS & AB	0.47	0.15	0.62	Partial Mediation
Moderation Analysis (Interaction Effect)				
Variable Interaction	β	t-value	p-value	
EC \times Institutional Support	0.22	2.98	0.004	

Farmer reaction to environmental change in the Pakistani agricultural fields cannot be considered as solitary choices because the farmers are influenced by institutional support networks and connections which inform their behavior. According to this research, the mediating factor between environmental change and adoption behavior is partially played by the factor of institutional support. Even though environmental change has a direct impact ($b = 0.47$), the fact that an indirect effect ($b = 0.15$) is significant adds the overall effect ($b = 0.62$). This is to mean that environmental stress like abnormal rainfall or pest outbreak does not only stimulate farmers to adapt, but also to utilize institutional processes like extension services and training programs. This trend is indicative of the reality in the world wherein farmers faced with risks of climate turn to external knowledge and technical support so as to make decisions. This mechanism is supported by empirical data, which supports the idea that institutional or organizational support

promotes the adoption of green technologies among farmers in indirect ways (e.g., by means of the increased capacity and resource availability) (Zhang et al., 2025). Hence organizational support is a channel of transmission, which transforms pressure on the environment into practicable innovation. Nevertheless, the mediation is biased, which means that local knowledge, personal experience, and peer interactions are also used by farmers. This indicates that the multidimensionality of adaptation behavior is not entirely based on formal institutions. The findings of the moderation further serve to support this story. The large interaction effect ($b = 0.22$, $p < 0.01$) shows that institutional support enhances the effect of environmental change on the adoption behavior. That is, when farmers are more exposed to the various extension services, subsidies and training; they will be in a better position to convert environmental challenges into innovative actions. An example is that two farmers might be subjected to the same climate pressure, but one with an institutional support is prone to embrace the smart practice of climate. The discovery is consistent with the recent empirical evidence that the supportive conditions and external resources play a major role in enhancing the effectiveness of the adoption decision and the behavioral response to the drivers of innovation (Yuan et al., 2025). It means that institutional support does not only make the process of adoption easier but makes farmers more responsive to change of environment. On the whole, the findings provide a simple narrative: change in the environment is one of the factors driving agricultural innovation, yet the latter can produce its results only when the institutional frameworks are strong. In the absence of it, farmers might be aware of environmental hazards but they are not able to act appropriately. As such, it is imperative to reinforce institutional systems to support the

idea of sustainable and climate-resilient agriculture.

Conclusion

The results of this research have made it clear that environmental change is an important factor determining the adoption behavior of farmers in the South Punjab, Pakistan. Climatic variability also affects farmers who have witnessed and experienced more variability due to climatic conditions like irregular rain, increased temperatures and outbreak of pests, are more likely to adopt climate-smart agricultural practices. This confirms the fact that the environment in its stress causes agricultural innovation and adaptive decision-making. The findings also indicate that institutional support is an important factor that influences the adoption behavior directly and indirectly. The availability of the extension services, training, subsidies and agricultural information plays a great role towards enabling farmers to be more responsive to the environmental challenges. The mediation analysis reveals that institutional support is partially the reason behind the relationship between environmental change and adoption behavior, which means that farmers use not only environmental cues but also institutional mechanisms to make decisions. Furthermore, in the study, the issue of economic limitations is identified as a significant obstructive factor to adoption. A lack of financial resources and high-cost inputs coupled with limited access to credit decreases the ability of farmers greatly to adopt innovative practices despite them being aware of the need to do so. The moderation findings equally confirm institutional support ensures the positive role of environmental change on adoption behavior, that is, farmers with improved institutional access are more susceptible to environmental pressures. All in all, the paper finds that the necessity of environmental change brings about the necessity of

innovation, but that

the practical implementation of agricultural practices is highly reliant on the institutional support and economic ability.

Recommendations

In relation to the outcomes of the current research, some major recommendations are made to improve the behavior of the farmers to adopt and implement climate-resilient agriculture in South Punjab. To start with, there is the urgent necessity to enhance the institution support systems, especially the agricultural extension services. Government and other agencies involved should increase the frontier and efficiency of extension programs, through frequent training, technical advice and field demonstrations of farmers. Such measures will facilitate the knowledge-practice gap and facilitate the use of modern and climate smart agricultural technologies. Second, it is necessary to enhance financial resources accessibility. The policymakers must implement policies that are friendly to the farmers such as credit schemes, low-interest loans and specific subsidies to minimize financial limitations. Smallholder and resource-poor farmers that are the most exposed to the economic shocks and environmental risks should be treated with special consideration. Loan processes also need to be streamlined and credit made available on time to enable farmers to invest in agriculture. The level of awareness should be stepped up in order to boost the knowledge of farmers regarding climate change and its effects. Farmers can be improved to interpret the changes in the environment and react properly through educational campaigns, workshops and training. Government agencies, research institutions, and the local communities should collaborate and this can be instrumental in spreading knowledge and best practices. Also, the use of climate-smart agriculture should be encouraged. These will involve promotion of the practice of crop diversification, effective water management,

planting of better seed varieties and integrated pest management. Policies can be introduced based on incentives that will encourage farmers to engage in such practices. Long term planning and constant policy support are needed in order to achieve sustainable agricultural development. Planners ought to come up with combined policies which can tackle the environmental, institutional, and economic challenges at the same time. By reinforcing these spheres, the adaptive capacity of farmers will be improved, agricultural productivity will increase, and long-term sustainability in the context of constant change of the environment will be ensured.

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